

EFFECT OF FAST SURYANAMASKAR ON OXYGEN SATURATION LEVEL OF COLLEGE CRICKET PLAYER

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of Fast Suryanamaskar on oxygen saturation level of college cricket player. There may not be any significant relationship between Surya Namaskar and Oxygen saturation. In the present study, thirty cricket players plays in regular basis in various colleges from Midnapore in West Bengal. The age of the subject ranged from 18-22 years was selected for research work. The selected subjects are Experimental group and they practiced Fast Suryanamaskar. Fast Suryanamaskar practices for five days per week for six weeks in the morning. The data collected without fast Suryanamaskar at baseline and immediately after the completion of fast Suryanamaskar and statistically analyzed using a t- test. The significant level was set at 0.05 level for this study. The present study drawn that suryanamaskar is a dynamic and here oxygen saturation is less after the Suryanamaskar practice. It's mean Oxygen demand in the human body.

Key Words: Suryanamaskar, Oxygen Saturation, Cricket

Introduction:

Surya Namaskar is an ancient Indian method of offering prayers to the rising Sun in the morning along with a series of twelve physical postures with regulated breathing aiming at range of physical, mental and spiritual benefits. Along with physical postures, Surya namaskar has specific spiritual connotations attached to it. Surya namaskar is a graceful combined sequence of twelve positions along with regulated breathing and relaxation. These alternating backward and forward bending figure flexible and stretch our spinal cord. The maximum range produces deep stretch to the total body. One round Surya Namaskar is much better workout at your home. It is essential for brain, lungs, blood circulation, nerve and makes the man healthier and best own upon him the help of a long life. Regular practice of Surya Namaskar breathing gives maximum benefits through complete utilization of the prana system. The incorporate of Surya Namaskar now a day in cricket brings fruitful result. That's why the application of Surya Namaskar as a warming up exercises and achieve the good respiratory position. So, here researcher chose the topic because oxygen saturation is very important in our sports field. Lots of exercise or tuff game situation is very much important for a player. Without breathing exhausted a player can play more time in the play field.

Statement of the Problem:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of Fast Suryanamaskar on oxygen saturation level of college cricket player.

Hypothesis:

There may not be any significant relationship between Surya Namaskar and Oxygen saturation.

Methodology:

Subject:

In the present study, thirty cricket players plays in regular basis in various colleges from Midnapore in West Bengal. The age of the subject ranged from 18-22 years was selected for research work.

Variables:

The selected subjects are Experimental group and they practiced Fast Suryanamaskar. Fast Suryanamaskar practices for five days per week for six weeks in the morning.

Experimental Procedure:

The selected numbers of thirty (30) subjects of college students those are played cricket in inter college level. Using 't' test in Pre-test and Post-test mean of the group to find out the difference among the selected variable in college students. Before and after the Fast Suryanamaskar data was collected through pulse oximeter on pulse oxygen and was analyzed. These sequences in Fast Suryanamaskar practice by subjects.

Series of Asanas in Suryanamaskar:

- Step 1: Prayer Pose- Pranamasana
- Step 2: Raised Arms Pose- Hastauttanasna
- Step 3: Hand To Foot Pose- Hasta Padasana
- Step 4: Equestrian Pose – Hasta Padasana
- Step 5: Stick Pose – Ashwa Sanchalanasana
- Step 6: Salute with Eight Parts or Points – Ashtanga Namaskara.
- Step 7: Cobra Pose – Bhujangasana
- Step 8: Mountain Pose – Parvatasana

- Step 9: Equestrian Pose –Ashwa Sanchalanasana
- Step 10: Hand to Foot Pose – Hasta Padasana
- Step 11: Raised Arms Pose – Hastauttanasna
- Step 12: Standing Mountain Pose - Tadasana

The subjects were trained to perform fast suryanamaskar in rapid manner so that all twelve (12) postures were completed in 2 minutes 6 rounds perform in 10 – 12 minutes.

Analysis of Data:

The data collected without fast Suryanamaskar at baseline and immediately after the completion of fast Suryanamaskar and statistically analyzed using a t- test. The significant level was set at 0.05 level for this study.

Findings:

Mean and standard deviation of personal data of the subject are tabulated and presented in the table 1.

Table 1: Mean, SD, DF and ‘t’ Test Value of Oxygen Saturation in the Surya Namaskar Practice Group (Significant at 0.05 level)

Test	N	Mean	SD	DF	‘t’
Pre-Test	30	98.6	1.06	38	2.69*
Post-Test	30	97.2	2.63		

Table 1 reveals that the pre-test means value of oxygen saturation was 98.6 and SD was 1.06 whereas post-test mean value of oxygen saturation was 97.2 and SD was 2.63 and ‘t’ value 2.69* where as significant difference was found at the level of 0.05 level.

Figure 1: Mean and SD of Pre-test and Post-test

Discussion:

In the present study before and after the Fast Suryanamaskar compared the oxygen saturation level. This study is the unique study to investigate the effect of Fast Suryanamaskar and oxygen saturation level of college cricket players. The result of the present study shows that the before the Fast Suryanamaskar oxygen saturation level is more, than after the Fast suryanamaskar oxygen saturation level. The series of Asanas in Suryanamaskar is very effective for a person. Here forward and backward bending asans is mainly constructed. In our human body all muscles and joints are much activated. We are general public also can doing this Suryanamaskar alternative of worming up. Significant relationship between suryanamaskar and oxygen saturation is calculated. Zijlstra WG et al. studied that Oxygen saturation (SO₂) should not be confused with oxyhaemoglobin fraction FHbO₂. As automated multiple wavelength photometers may yield both SO₂ and FHbO₂, care should be taken that only SO₂ is used in checking the results of pulse oximeter. Arterial SO₂ is the quantity aimed at by pulse oximeter. Although the accuracy of the measurement may be less than that of the analysis of an arterial blood sample in vitro, the measured quantity remains SO₂. Using a special symbol, like SpO₂, obscures this fact and should be discouraged.

Conclusion:

Based on the reviews and results the following conclusions were drawn. The present study drawn that suryanamaskar is a dynamic and here oxygen saturation is less after the Suryanamaskar practice. It’s mean Oxygen demand in the human body.

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